

FINANCIAL TREND AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY IN BANGLADESH: A STUDY ON BEXIMCO PHARMACEUTICALS LIMITED

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ABSTRACT

Financial trend and performance analysis are the vital tools for measuring the efficiency of management in different aspects of a company. Financial trend and performance have been evaluated in the study through analyzing the financial statement i.e. through ratio analysis. Solvency, profitability, activity or turnover and return on assets and equity, earning per share, dividend per share, dividend pay-out ratio, market value per share, price-earning ratio, price-equity ratio, net operating cash flow per share have been analyzed to measure the financial trend, performance and efficiency of management. To measure the financial strengths and weaknesses of the company is the main objective of the study. This study is empirical in nature and mainly based on secondary data which are collected from annual reports of Beximco Pharmaceuticals Ltd.. Data of 06-year ranging from 2013 to 2018-2019 have been used for conducting the research work. Some ratios, statistical tools and percentages have been used for analyzing and interpreting the data. This study is following the pharmaceutical industry with special reference to “Beximco Pharmaceuticals Ltd.” Proper financial performance of manufacturing sub-sector like pharmaceutical sub-sector may be helpful for preparing fiscal and economic policy of the country. From the findings of the study, it may be said that liquidity position and activity ratios are not so much optimistic while the profitability, debt and market ratios are satisfactory. From overall findings of the study, it is inferred that Beximco Pharmaceuticals Ltd. is running with positive trend as well as stable performance. Ultimately, the study recommends to increase sales and reduce fixed expenses and to be more careful in handling operating expenses of the firm.

Keywords: Financial performance, trend analysis, liquidity, profitability, turnover ratios, Earning per share, dividend per share, annual report.